

Perceived Influence of Occupational Stress on Job Performance of High-Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities

Amie-Ogan, O. T. PhD & Epele, Glory Onyekaozuru

Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt

Corresponding Authors' Email: tekena.amie-ogan@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

This study examined perceived influence of occupational stress on job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities. Three objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The total population of the study was 159 consisting of 14 Deans of Faculties, 79 Heads of Departments and 8 Directors of Centres from Rivers State University and 6 Deans of Faculties, 37 Heads of Departments and 15 Directors of Centres from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The population was manageable enough, so the researchers used the entire population, adopting census sampling method. The data collecting instrument for the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled: "Perceived Influence of Occupational Stress on Job Performance of High-Profile Lecturers Questionnaire" which was on a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent, High Extent, Low Extent and Very Low Extent. The instrument was face and content validated by three experts from the Department of Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation respectively all in Rivers State University and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability indexes of 0.84, 0.86 and 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that to a high extent workload stress, student-related stress and work-life balance stress influence job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that recruitment of additional academic staff should be prioritized to reduce excessive workloads and prevent burnout among lecturers.

Keywords: *Occupational Stress, Job Performance, Workload Stress, Student-Related Stress, Work-Life Balance Stress.*

INTRODUCTION

University education is tasked with the responsibility of knowledge creation and knowledge transmission. It serves as a bridge between academic knowledge and real-world applications, empowering individuals to solve complex problems and contributing meaningfully to the societal development. According to Amie-Ogan and Epelle (2023), university education equips students with requisite knowledge, skills and abilities as well as rekindles such entrepreneurial spirit to aid them emerge as a force to reckon with in the world of work and self-reliance. These characteristics of university education have kept it at the very heart of the knowledge sector. There is no gainsaying that the university education of any nation is vital because it prepares individuals for careers, research and personal development and plays a crucial role in economic growth and social development. The necessity for universities to excel in their role of knowledge creation is crucial for the survival of any society in this modern age and to keep up with the dynamism of the world.

Governments all over the world recognize the significance of university education. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) explicitly outlined the goals of tertiary education which include university education in her National Policy on Education which include to: contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower training; develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual and society; develop the intellectual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate their local and external environments; acquire both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society; promote and encourage scholarship and community service; forge and cement national unity; and promote national and international understanding and interaction.

The fulfilment of these goals depends to a large extent on the job performance of lecturers. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) in her National Policy on Education, also asserted that “no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers”. In agreement, Osaat and Ekechukwu (2017), posited that lecturers are the major stakeholders in the university industry. The lecturers are the key personnel directly involved in getting the students educationally trained and have educational programmes implemented. Their primary responsibilities are to teach and bring up the young generation of students to acquire skills and knowledge for personal growth and social development. High profile lecturers in the university include Professors, Readers, Senior Lecturers, Deans of Faculties, Heads of Departments and Directors of Institutes. In order to achieve university predetermined goals, these lecturers are maximally engaged in several academic activities. These activities make them susceptible to occupational stress due to the multifaceted nature of their job, which encompass teaching, research, administrative duties, student mentorship and community service (Aondongu, Owoyemi, Atoyebi & Luga, 2024). The increasing demands placed on lecturers to meet academic standards, publish research works and engage in professional development often create a stressful work environment, which can affect their job performance and overall well-being (Gao, Zhang & Li, 2022).

Job performance refers to the effectiveness with which an individual carries out their duties, responsibilities and task associated with their role in an organization. Okebukola (2021), defined job performance as the quality, efficiency and consistency of an employees’ work output in achieving set goals and contributing to organizational success. Adejumobi and Ojikutu (2018), noted that indicators of lecturers’ job performance include adequate lesson preparation and presentation, mastery of subject, class participation and control, evaluation of students through tests, assignments and examinations, periodic assessment of students and decision making. There is no doubt that lecturing job in Nigerian universities is a herculean task considering the heavy workload associated with it. Lecturers are made to teach many courses of different programmes such as regular, part-time and sandwich undergraduate, pre-degree, postgraduate regular and sandwich programmes as well as open and distance education. Aside from these responsibilities, lecturers in universities in Rivers State and Nigeria at large also have other statutory duties such as supervision of students research work (undergraduate and postgraduate), coordinatorship of various programmes, examination officers, directors, deans, heads of departments, members of various committees in the university, conference attendance and publication of journal papers and books (Amie-Ogan & Fekarurhobo, 2021). These activities may lead to stress which may hinder them from performing their job effectively.

Lecturers have been saddled with too much academic work and have lost the ability to identify and manage work stress and associated ailments. According to Amie-Ogan, Epelle and Oguru (2023), the step-wise progression of teaching from one level to another without holidays or annual leave for lecturers is cumbersome for so many of them. It was perceived that so many have retired to their early graves while others labour under stress related ill health such as heart palpitation, hypertension, diabetes, gastric ulcer, hepatitis, cancer, tiredness, cardiac arrest etcetera. It is against this background that this study hopes to examine, Perceived Influence of Occupational Stress on Job Performance of High Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Concept of Occupational Stress

Stress is the body’s response to excessive work demands. World Health Organization (2020), described stress as the response people may have when presented with work demands and pressures that are not matched to their knowledge and abilities and which challenge their ability to cope. Occupational stress refers to the physical, emotional and mental strain or pressure that individuals experience due to demands or challenges related to their work. Jeon, Yoon and Yang (2022), defined occupational stress as the total amount of negative psychological responses that workers experience during job

performance. According to Haque and Yamoah (2021), occupational stress arises from various work-related demands and pressures, leading to physiological and psychological responses that can negatively impact employee performance. Occupational stress is the emotional reaction and harm that happens when a job's requirement does not match the workers' skills, needs or resources (Kavitha & Kumar, 2023). Prolonged exposure to workplace stress can result in health problems such as hypertension, anxiety, depression and other stress-related illnesses (Chukwuemeka & Nwosu, 2023). For instance, the Postgraduate School guideline of Rivers State University states that the number of postgraduate students' thesis and dissertation to be supervised at a particular time are 2 PhD and 3 Masters for Professors and Readers, 1 PhD and 3 Masters for senior lecturers and 2 Masters for lecturer I (Rivers State University Post Graduate Handbook in Amie-Ogan & Fekarurhobo, 2021). But given the fact that the staff/students ratio is not balanced, most lecturers are made to supervise more than the stipulated number of students. This may be the reason why lecturers in the universities have been found to suffer sicknesses stress prone such as cardiac arrest, hypertension and other related ailments which have caused eminent deaths in the school system. Ofoegbu and Alonge (2021), asserted that occupational stress arises from various sources, including workload stress, student-related stress and work-life balance stress. When the demands and pressures placed on individual workers do not match the resources which are available, either from the organization or within the individual, stress can occur and endanger that person's health and well-being (Ajayi, Jones & Unuigbo, 2019). Heidi in Amie-Ogan and Michael (2023), defined stress as the body's response to excessive work demands. In a related vein, the World Health Organization (2020), defined work related stress as the response to demands and pressures that challenge an individual's coping abilities.

The concept of occupational stress has garnered significant attention from researchers and policymakers, particularly due to its implications on employee well-being, productivity and organizational performance. Occupational stress arises when there is a perceived imbalance between job demands and the individual's ability to cope, resulting in negative health and job performance outcomes. According to Ates and Ihtiyaroglu (2019), occupational stress might lead to lower productivity, lower commitment, increased absenteeism, high turnover, job disengagement, high work pressure, job dissatisfaction, low attachment, low level of loyalty as well as turning individuals to imbibing wrong behavioural patterns thus diminishing work-life quality. Common stressors associated with high profile lecturers include high job demands, lack of organizational support, job insecurity, and poor work-life balance. These stressors often lead to burnout, decreased job satisfaction, increased turnover intentions and reduced productivity. For instance, in the education sector, lecturers face stress from heavy workloads and challenging student behaviour, impacting job satisfaction and student outcomes. Administrative demands and lack of support further exacerbate stress levels. Consequently, stress leads to reduced job satisfaction among lecturers, which negatively impacts their teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. The Canadian Center for Occupational Health and Safety (2020), defined workplace stress as the harmful physical and emotional responses that can result from conflicts between job demands on the employee and the amount of control an employee has over meeting these demands. Occupational stress is one of the main causes of low productivity, rising costs, increased errors, increased absenteeism and high turnover rate. Employees who are under stress make unwise decisions, thus working under stress can result in physical and psychological impairments.

Influence of Work Load Stress on Job Performance of Lecturers

Workload stress refers to the psychological and emotional strain experienced by individuals when they perceive that the demands of their job exceed their capacity to meet them within available time and resources. In the academic context, workload stress arises when lecturers are burdened with excessive teaching hours, large class sizes, administrative duties and the pressure to conduct research and publish

findings (Ajayi & Olamide, 2022). Excessive workload, including administrative duties, supervision of numerous undergraduate and postgraduate projects and teaching multiple courses within a semester, has been shown to adversely affect lecturers' productivity. It interferes with lecturers' ability to prepare adequately for classes, engage in research activities and fulfil other academic responsibilities. Furthermore, involvement in multiple committees has been identified as significant stressors that correlate with reduced job performance among lecturers. A study examining this relationship found a very strong positive correlation between these factors and decreased job performance, suggesting that as lecturers' committee involvements increase, their job performance declines (Akpomie & Elenga-Ikenga, 2023). Chen, Zhang and Lee (2020), emphasized that the multifaceted responsibilities of lecturers, including teaching, research and administrative duties, contributed to unclear expectations and increased workload, leading to elevated stress levels. Workload of lecturers is said to be excess when the volume of task expected to be performed by a lecturer surpasses or goes beyond the statutory limit or national/global benchmark. The issue of excess workload arises when the workload exceeds the usual statutory routine, the earmarked time, general capacity of an average lecturer and other requisite resources needed to perform the job. Kaborloomene (2023), stated that lecturers might experience stress due to an overwhelming number of lectures to prepare and deliver or the need to meet stringent research targets or administrative duties. Adeolu and Arinze (2018), reported that 78% of lecturers feel they don't have enough planning time to properly plan and deliver their lessons because of the number of courses they have to teach in a particular term or semester. Research by Kinman and Wray (2018), underscores that excess workload is a major contributor to job dissatisfaction and reduced productivity among university lecturers, as it diverts time and energy away from core academic activities. This imbalance leads to stress which in some cases breeds the intentions to leave the academic profession altogether. A study by Adekola (2019), found that lecturers burdened with excessive workload reported lower levels of research output and diminished classroom performance. The constant pressure to meet deadlines, coupled with the need to maintain academic excellence, can lead to cognitive overload, reducing lecturers' ability to concentrate as a result of stress.

Influence of Student-Related Stress on Job Performance of Lecturers

Student-related stress refers to the psychological strain experienced by lecturers due to challenges associated with handling students' academic and behavioural issues. These challenges include managing large class sizes, supervising students' projects and theses, addressing students' academic needs and dealing with disciplinary matters (Akpan & Musa, 2022). Smith, Brown and Lee (2022), opined that managing large classes such as preparing lectures, grading and providing individualized feedback contributes significantly to stress levels and impair lecturers' ability to deliver quality teaching. One of the primary ways student-related stress influences job performance of lecturers is through its impact on lecturers' emotional well-being. When lecturers face persistent challenges such as students' lack of motivation, non-compliance with deadlines or academic dishonesty, it can lead to feelings of frustration, anxiety and emotional exhaustion. This emotional toll can diminish their enthusiasm for teaching and reduce their ability to create engaging and innovative learning environment, ultimately affecting their job performance. A research by Patel, Johnson and Kim (2023), found that lecturers under significant student-related stress exhibited impaired decision-making and reduced ability to concentrate on core academic tasks. This often resulted in delays in grading, lower-quality feedback and less effective curriculum delivery, thereby reducing the overall quality of education. Amie-Ogan and Fekarurhobo (2021), asserted that the act of teaching many courses and supervision of large number of undergraduates and post-graduate students constitute some of the workload that can influence the job performance of lecturers at the tertiary education level. For example, some lecturers could teach large class sizes ranging from 150 – 400 per semester causing lecture rooms to be overcrowded. In some

cases, lecturers are found to supervise over 30 undergraduate and postgraduate research projects. This leaves them working all through the year with little or no break.

Influence of Work-Life Balance Stress on Job Performance of Lecturers

Work-life balance stress refers to the tension that arises when individuals struggle to meet the competing demands of their professional and personal lives. For university lecturers, this type of stress occurs when excessive job responsibilities, such as teaching, research and administrative duties encroach on their personal time, leaving little room for family, social activities and self-care (Oladimeji & Bello, 2024). A research by Aluko (2019), highlighted that lecturers who work excessively long hours report higher levels of work-life conflict, which adversely affects their emotional well-being and reduces their capacity to perform effectively in their academic roles. Consequently, this interferes with their health, sleep and relationship with their families. A study by Adekola (2019), found that lecturers experiencing work-life imbalance are more likely to disengage from their professional duties, leading to increased absenteeism. When personal obligations are consistently neglected due to work demands, it creates resentment and a sense of dissatisfaction with their job, which affects lecturers' commitment to their roles. These factors do not only reduce individual performance but also affect institutional effectiveness, as students and academic programmes suffer from a lack of consistent, high-quality teaching and guidance. The inability to balance work responsibilities with personal life has a profound impact on lecturers' job performance, as it disrupts their ability to effectively manage their professional and personal commitments. Long working hours that encroach on personal time and limit time for family have a profound impact on lecturers' job performance, as they create a persistent conflict between professional obligations and personal priorities. Lecturers often work extended hours to meet the demands of teaching, research, student mentorship and administrative duties. These extended hours reduce the time available for family and personal activities, leading to stress, dissatisfaction and burnout. Ahmad, Omar and Hashim (2019), asserted that work-life imbalance caused by long hours is strongly correlated with decreased job satisfaction and diminished teaching effectiveness. Lecturers under such conditions often struggle to prepare adequately for lectures or provide meaningful feedback to students, ultimately compromising the quality of education. Furthermore, the inability to balance family and work responsibilities can hinder their participation in collaborative research or professional development activities, as their energy and time are consumed by work-related stress. Goh, Pfeffer and Zenios (2023), emphasized that lecturers dealing with chronic work-life conflict are less likely to engage positively with their peers, which further impacts their performance and the overall morale of the academic community. In addition, the inability to allocate time for personal growth or leisure activities undermines lecturers' overall satisfaction with their profession. Research has shown that when lecturers achieve a balance between their work and personal life, they experience increased productivity, improved well-being, and enhanced job performance. Conversely, poor work-life balance can lead to burnout, decreased motivation, and impaired cognitive function, ultimately affecting lecturers' ability to deliver quality instruction (Frone, 2018; Maslach & Leiter, 2018). Maintaining a healthy work-life balance is essential for lecturers to deliver quality instruction and achieve job satisfaction. Therefore, academic institutions must prioritize work-life balance policies and support systems to promote lecturers' well-being and job performance.

Statement of the Problem

University education in Nigeria is perceived by Nigerian youths and parents as a gateway to having a good job and bright future and this notion has put a lot of responsibilities on lecturers in universities. Lecturers are known to be responsible for the quality of education dispensed per time in their universities. In fulfilling this task, university lecturers are expected to perform multiple roles, including teaching, research, administrative duties and student mentorship, often under challenging conditions.

The increasing demands placed on lecturers, coupled with inadequate institutional support, create a stressful work environment that can negatively affect their job performance.

It has been observed that high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities are overburdened with too many work responsibilities which encroach on their personal time, leaving them with little room for their family, social activities and self-care thus making it difficult for them to perform at their best. Lecturers are assigned to teach so many courses to teach, expected to publish research articles in reputable journals for promotion, write books and participate in conferences, workshops, seminar, supervise students' projects from undergraduate to postgraduate level and also handle administrative positions etcetera. The workload is further compounded with population explosion in the public universities in Rivers State where the ratio of lecturers to students is 1:100 students or more especially in Engineering courses and Law as against the National Universities Commission (NUC) Benchmark Minimum Academic Standard (BMAS) recommendation of 1:30 (1 lecturer to 30 students) for Faculty of Education, Agricultural Science 1:15, Art 1:30, Engineering 1:15, Law 1:30, Management Sciences 1:30, Science 1:20, Social Sciences 1:30 (NUC in Amie-Ogan & Fekarurhobo, 2021). These challenges pose threats on the job performance expectations of lecturers. The question now is, does occupational stress influence job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities? This study provided answers to the question posed through investigating, "Perceived Influence of Occupational Stress on Job Performance of High-Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities".

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine perceived influence of occupational stress on job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. examine the extent workload stress influence job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.
2. determine the extent student-related stress influence job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.
3. ascertain the extent work-life balance stress influence job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does workload stress influence job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities?
2. To what extent does student-related stress influence job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities?
3. To what extent does work-life balance stress influence job performance of high-profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

- Ho₁ There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent workload stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.
- Ho₂ There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent student-related stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Ho₃ There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 159 lecturers consisting of 14 Deans of Faculties, 79 Heads of Departments and 8 Directors of Centres from Rivers State University totalling 101 and 6 Deans of Faculties, 37 Heads of Departments and 15 Directors of Centres from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education totalling 58. The entirety of the population was used which infers census sampling method was used. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled: “Perceived Influence of Occupational Stress on Job Performance Questionnaire (PIOSJPQ)” which was validated by three (3) experts, one (1) from the Department of Educational Management and two (2) from Measurement and Evaluation respectively in Rivers State University. The instrument was structured on a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) with values 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The reliability of the instrument was established using the Cronbach Alpha method which yielded reliability indexes of 0.84, 0.86 and 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions with a criterion mean of 2.50. Questionnaire items with ratings below 2.50 denoted ‘Low Extent while 2.50 and above signified ‘High Extent. The hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. Analysed data therefore with calculated z-value greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 was rejected and below was accepted.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does workload stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of High Profile Lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent Workload Stress Influence Job Performance of High Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

S/ N	Item	RSU N=101		Decisio n	IAUE N=58		Decisio n
		\bar{X}	SD		\bar{X}	SD	
1	Multiple course allocation reduces lecturers’ ability to prepare adequately for classes	3.48	1.02	VHE	3.49	1.05	VHE
2	Committee participation interfere with lecturers teaching effectiveness	3.43	1.05	VHE	3.42	1.02	VHE
3	Departmental coordinatorship affects lecturers’ ability to cover up the course outlines before the end of the semester	3.51	1.06	VHE	3.32	1.04	VHE
4	The need to continuously write and publish papers reduces lecturers’ ability to engage students effectively	3.54	1.10	VHE	3.36	1.07	VHE
5	Lecturers fail to meet the deadline for submission of results when they have excessive teaching loads	3.45	1.02	VHE	3.50	1.08	VHE
Grand Mean/SD		3.48	1.05		3.42	1.06	

Source: Researcher’s Field Study (2025)

Data in Table 1 above for Research Question 1, revealed that all the items (1-5) had mean values of 3.48, 3.43, 3.51, 3.54 and 3.45 with standard deviation 1.02, 1.05, 1.06, 1.10 and 1.02 for high profile lecturers in Rivers State University and 3.49, 3.42, 3.32, 3.36 and 3.30 with standard deviation 1.05, 1.02, 1.04, 1.07 and 1.08 for high profile lecturers in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. In summary, with grand mean values of 3.48 and 3.42 which are above the criterion mean of 2.50, this indicated that workload stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities to a very high extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent does student-related stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of High Profile Lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent Student-Related Stress Influence Job Performance of High Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

S/N	Item	RSU N=101			IAUE N=58		
		\bar{X}	SD	Decision	\bar{X}	S	Decision
6	Teaching students from various programmes at the same time reduces lecturers' ability to balance teaching and mentorship duties	3.45	1.05	VHE	3.50	1.08	VHE
7	Handling large students' population in lectures reduces lecturers' ability to engage students effectively	3.51	1.06	VHE	3.41	1.02	VHE
8	Research supervision of many students at a time makes it difficult for lecturers to critically look at each student's work	3.45	1.05	VHE	3.25	1.06	VHE
9	Frequent students' consultations on academic, career and personal matters affects lecturers' effectiveness in carrying out academic duties	3.35	1.09	VHE	3.43	1.07	VHE
10	Handling students' disciplinary issues such as academic dishonesty, classroom disruptions and lack of commitment to learning affects lecturers' ability to deliver quality instruction	3.46	1.12	VHE	3.44	1.08	VHE
Grand Mean/SD		3.44	1.07		3.41	1.06	

Source: *Researcher's Field Study (2025)*

Table 2 above for Research Question 2, revealed that all the items (7-10) had mean values of 3.45, 3.51, 3.45, 3.35 and 3.46 with standard deviation 1.05, 1.06, 1.05, 1.09 and 1.12 for high profile lecturers in Rivers State University and 3.50, 3.41, 3.25, 3.43 and 3.44 with standard deviation 1.08, 1.02, 1.06, 1.07 and 1.08 for high profile lecturers in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. In summary, with grand mean values of 3.44 and 3.41 which are above the criterion mean of 2.50, this indicated that student-related stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities to a very high extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent does work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of High Profile Lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent Work-Life Balance Stress Influence Job Performance of High Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

S/N	Item	RSU N=101			IAUE N=58		
		\bar{X}	SD	Decision	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	Multiple job responsibilities limits lecturers' ability to maintain a healthy family life which affects their job performance	3.47	1.02	VHE	3.45	1.04	VHE
12	Pressure to meet deadlines leads to reduced job efficiency among lecturers	3.35	1.09	VHE	3.43	1.02	VHE
13	Inability to balance work responsibilities with family commitments affects lecturers teaching effectiveness	3.54	1.00	VHE	3.36	1.01	VHE
14	Limited time for socialization due to heavy academic responsibilities reduces lecturers' social activities which affects their job performance	3.46	1.02	VHE	3.44	1.04	VHE
15	Limited flexibility in work schedule prevents lecturers effective managing of personal and professional commitments which reduces their teaching effectiveness	3.45	1.06	VHE	3.47	1.08	VHE
Grand Mean/SD		3.45	1.03		3.43	1.04	

Source: *Researcher's Field Study (2025)*

Table 3 above for Research Question 3, revealed that all the items (11-15) had mean values of 3.47, 3.35, 3.54, 3.46 and 3.45 with standard deviation 1.02, 1.09, 1.00, 1.02 and 1.06 for high profile lecturers in Rivers State University and 3.45, 3.43, 3.36, 3.44 and 3.47 with standard deviation 1.04, 1.02, 1.01, 1.04 and 1.08 for high profile lecturers in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. In summary, with grand mean values of 3.45 and 3.43 which are above the criterion mean of 2.50, this indicated that work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities to a very high extent.

Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent workload stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4.6: z-test Analysis of Difference Between the Mean Ratings of High Profile Lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent Workload Stress Influence Job Performance of High Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
RSU	101	3.48	1.05					
				157	0.05	0.30	±1.96	Ho ₁ Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
IAUE	58	3.42	1.06					

Source: *Researcher's Field Study (2025)*

Table 4 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on

the extent workload stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities. The z- calculated value was 0.30 while the z-critical value was ± 1.96 , at 0.05 level of significance with 157 degree of freedom. Since the z-calculated value of 0.30 was less than the z-critical value ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent workload stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent student-related stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Table 5: z-test Analysis of Difference Between the Mean Ratings of High Profile Lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent Student-Related Stress Influence Job Performance of High Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
RSU	101	3.44	1.07					
				157	0.05	0.15	± 1.96	Ho ₂ Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
IAUE	58	3.41	1.06					

Source: Researcher's Field Study (2025)

Table 5 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent student-related stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities. The z- calculated value was 0.15 while the z-critical value was ± 1.96 , at 0.05 level of significance with 157 degree of freedom. Since the z-calculated value of 0.15 was less than the z-critical value ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent student-related stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Table 6: z-test Analysis of Difference Between the Mean Ratings of High Profile Lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent Work-Life Balance Stress Influence Job Performance of High Profile Lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
RSU	101	3.45	1.03					
				157	0.05	0.11	± 1.96	Ho ₃ Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
IAUE	58	3.43	1.04					

Source: Researcher's Field Study (2025)

Table 6 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities. The z- calculated value was 0.11 while the z-critical value was ± 1.96 , at 0.05 level of significance with 157 degree of freedom. Since the z-calculated value of 0.11 was less than the z-critical value ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Discussion of Findings

Findings on Research Question 1 on Table 1 revealed that workload stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities to a very high extent with grand mean values of 3.48 and 3.42. Hypothesis 1 on Table 4 showed that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent workload stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities with z-calculated value of 0.30 which was less than z-critical value of ± 1.96 . The finding is in agreement with Chen, Zhang and Lee (2020), who emphasized that the multifaceted responsibilities of lecturers, including teaching, research and administrative duties, contributed to unclear expectations and increased workload, leading to elevated stress levels. This finding is in consonance with Kaborloomene (2023), who stated that lecturers might experience stress due to an overwhelming number of lectures to prepare and deliver or the need to meet stringent research targets or administrative duties.

Findings on Research Question 2 on Table 2 revealed that student-related stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities to a very high extent with grand mean values of 3.44 and 3.41. Hypothesis 2 on Table 5 showed that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent student-related stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities with z-calculated value of 0.15 which was less than z-critical value of ± 1.96 . This finding is in agreement with Smith, Brown and Lee (2022), who opined that managing large classes such as preparing lectures, grading and providing individualized feedback contributes significantly to stress levels and impair lecturers' ability to deliver quality teaching. This finding corroborates with a research by Patel, Johnson and Kim (2023), who found that lecturers under significant student-related stress exhibited impaired decision-making and reduced ability to concentrate on core academic tasks.

Findings on Research Question 3 on Table 3 revealed that work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities to a very high extent with grand mean values of 3.45 and 3.43. Hypothesis 3 on Table 6 showed that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of high profile lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities with z-calculated value of 0.11 which was less than z-critical value of ± 1.96 . This finding is related to a research by Aluko (2019), who highlighted that lecturers who work excessively long hours report higher levels of work-life conflict, which adversely affects their emotional well-being and reduces their capacity to perform effectively in their academic roles. This finding is in line with a study by Ahmad, Omar and Hashim (2019), who found that work-life imbalance caused by long hours is strongly correlated with decreased job satisfaction and diminished teaching effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that workload stress, student-related stress and work-life balance stress influence job performance of high profile lecturers in Rivers State Universities to a very high extent. Excess workload leading to stress causes lack of concentration which results in diminishing job performance of lecturers. Reducing workload, providing adequate resources and ensuring job security, can help to mitigate the effects of occupational stress and improve lecturers' job performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Recruitment of additional academic staff should be prioritized to reduce excessive workloads and prevent burnout among lecturers.
2. University management should offer regular workshops on classroom management, emotional intelligence and student engagement to help lecturers cope with difficult student behaviors.
3. University management should promote policies that allow for flexible work hours and remote working options where feasible, to help lecturers manage personal and professional responsibilities.

References

- Adejumobi, F. T. & Ojikutu, R. K. (2018). School climate and teacher job performance in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Discourse Journal of Educational Research*, 1(2), 26-36.
- Adekola, B. (2019). Work-life balance in the Nigerian banking sector. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1–14.
- Adeolu, J. A. & Arinze, P. A. (2018). Teachers' instructional workload management and students' academic performance in public and private secondary schools in Akoko North-East Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Linguistics*, 1(1), 1-15.
- Ahmad, A., Omar, Z. & Hashim, M. Z. (2019). Work-family conflict, stress, and job performance: A study of lecturers in Malaysian higher education institutions. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 11(3), 240–254.
- Ajayi, K. T. & Olamide, F. S. (2022). Exploring occupational stress and its effects on academic staff performance in Nigerian universities. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Management*, 14(3), 45-59.
- Ajayi, S. O., Jones, W. & Unuigbo, M. (2019). Occupational stress management for UK construction professionals: Understanding the causes and strategies for improvement. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 17(4), 819–832.
- Akpan, T. U. & Musa, J. A. (2022). The impact of student-related stress on university lecturers' job performance. *Journal of Higher Education Studies*, 15(4), 89-102.
- Akpomie, M. E. & Elenga-Ikenga, C. S. (2023). Excess workload and lecturers' job performance in faculties of education in Rivers State Universities. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 11(3):93-105.
- Aluko, Y. A. (2019). Work-family conflict and coping strategies adopted by women in academia. *Gender and Behaviour*, 7(1), 2095–2122.
- Amie-Ogan, O. T. & Epelle, V. J. (2023). Politics in the management of higher education and tertiary education goals attainment in Rivers State. *Rivers State University Faculty of Education Conference Journal*, 3(2), 1-14.

- Amie-Ogan, O. T. & Fekarurhobo, B. E. (2021). Perceived influence of work overload on academic staff job performance in universities in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research* 9(2), 56-67
- Amie-Ogan, O. T. & Michael, F. O. (2023). Work stress management strategies and teachers' productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 2(4), 53-67.
- Amie-Ogan, O. T., Epelle, V. J. & Oguru, (2023). Utilization of global workplace adaptations for enhanced academic staff productivity in Rivers State Universities. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 1(3), 24-40
- Aondongu, A. A., Owoyemi, J. O., Atoyebi, T. A. & Luga, T. (2024). Work stress as predictor of job performance among academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Kogi Journal of Politics*, 4(1), 61-80.
- Ates, O.T. & Ihtiyaroglu, N. (2019). Analysis of the relationship between stress and organizational commitment in employees: a meta-analysis study. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 7(1), 94-106.
- Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety. (2020). Workplace stress-general. Retrieved April 23, 2015 from <http://www.ccons.ca/oshanswers/psychosocial/stress>.
- Chen, C., Zhang, Z. & Lee, L. (2020). Exploring the relationship between role ambiguity and lecturers' stress levels in a Chinese University. *Asian Journal of Educational Psychology*, 32(2), 219-234
- Chukwuemeka, P. & Nwosu, E. (2023). Stress-related health challenges among academic staff in Nigerian universities. *Journal of Health and Wellness in Education*, 8(1), 67-82.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National policy on education*. Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC).
- Frone, M. R. (2018). Work-family balance. In J. C. Quick & L. E. Tetrick (Eds.), *Handbook of occupational health psychology* (pp. 143-162). American Psychological Association.
- Gao, L., Zhang, Y. & Li, H. (2022). Occupational stress and job performance: A systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Leadership*, 15(2), 21-40.
- Goh, J., Pfeffer, J. & Zenios, S. A. (2023). The relationship between workplace stressors and mortality and health costs in the United States. *Management Science*, 69(2), 425-439.
- Haque, A.U. & Yamoah, F.A. (2021). The role of ethical leadership in managing occupational stress to promote innovative work behaviour: A Cross-cultural management perspective. *Sustainability*, 13(17), 11-21.
- Jeon, M. K., Yoon, H. & Yang, Y. (2022). Emotional dissonance, job stress and intrinsic motivation of married women working in call centers: The roles of work overload and work-family conflict. *Administrative Sciences*, 12(1), 1055-1072.
- Kaborloomene, B. (2023). Sources of stress among lecturers in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Healthcare Research*, 11(4), 143-151.
- Kavitha, M. & Kumar, V. P. (2023). Effects of occupational stress on employee productivity: A study with reference to insurance sector employees in Chennai. *The Online Journal of Distance Education and e-Learning*, 11(2), 2120-2129.
- Kinman, G. & Wray, S. (2018). Presenteeism in academic employees: Occupational and individual factors. *Occupational Medicine*, 68(1), 46-50.
- Maslach, C. & Leiter, M. P. (2016). Understanding the burnout experience: Recent research and its implications for psychiatry. *World Psychiatry*, 15(2), 103-111.
- Ofoegbu, F. I. & Alonge, S. (2021). Role conflict, job insecurity and occupational stress among university lecturers. *West African Journal of Educational Management*, 9(3), 55-73.

- Okebukola, P. A. (2021). *Higher education reforms in Africa: Challenges and prospects*. Lagos: University Press.
- Oladimeji, A. O. & Bello, K. A. (2024). Managing occupational stress in higher education: The role of work-life balance strategies. *Journal of Educational Policy and Leadership Studies*, 11(2), 78-92.
- Osaat, D. S. & Ekechukwu, R. (2017). Managing workload of academic staff for job effectiveness in Nigeria Universities: a study of University of Port Harcourt in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*, 4 (12), 102-108.
- Patel, R., Johnson, T. & Kim, H. (2023). The effects of student-related stress on lecturers' cognitive functioning: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 29(1), 87-102.
- Postgraduate School guideline of Rivers State University (2013). *Post graduate school guideline*. Port Harcourt. SABCOS Printers & Publishers.
- Smith, J. D., Brown, P. K. & Lee, S. W. (2022). Chronic stress and job performance: Insights from educators in large classroom settings. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 34(3), 297-312.
- World Health Organization (2020). What is stress? Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-answers/item/stress-text%20,require%20access%20to%20health%20care>.
- World Health Organization. (2020). *Doing What Matters in Times of Stress: An Illustrated Guide*.